

Study on The Perception Of Bank Executives on Customer relationship Management Practices in selected banks in Bengaluru.

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ABSTRACT

In a service sector dominated economy like Indian Economy, customer relationship management practices plays a key role in acquisition of new customers and retention of existing customers by service entities. The growth of the economy can be accelerated by financially strong banking and financial services sector. The financial strength of this sector depends on their customer satisfaction. The needs and expectations of their customers is constantly changing with the innovations in services and delivery modes. Therefore the key issue here is to identify the kind of services expected by the customers and whether the banks have understood their expectations and adopted CRM practices to meet them.

Hence, study was carried out to understand the perception of bank executives on customer relationship management practices in selected banks operating in Bengaluru district of Karnataka. Response to the questionnaire from hundred bank executives were collected and analyzed. After analyzing the data using **Factor Analysis** it was observed that the impact of CRM practices can be broadly classified under two factors namely, **Effective banking services and security factors**.

Key words : Customer relationship management , factor analysis, perception, bank executives.

Introduction

Customer relationship management is an approach to managing a company interaction with current and potential customers. In this they use data about the customer from the customer history with a company and also they use data to improve the business relationship or services with the customer so that they focus on the customer retention and ultimately satisfy them. The CRM practices are adopted to generate better understanding of the customers for product development, segmentation, targeting, campaign management and maintenance of long term profitable and mutually beneficial relationships with customers. Customer is the king in all the business and forget the meaning of royal treatment of customers, many of the organizations are not treating the customer with dignity at least they should answer few simple questions after making them wait for long time, they should have at least some basic standards. Bank as a service organization have excellent reasons to adopt a comprehensive CRM strategy. Customer needs, wants, and desires keep changing day by day. Therefore it is necessary for the banks to adopt the changes in the market through tracking the customer wants and the needs. This is possible only when the organization has a close contact with its customers. Since customer is the lifeblood of any business organization and customer creation cost is costlier than customer retention cost, thus bank adopt CRM techniques for maintaining life relationship and by which they ensure customer loyalty and retention. Thus the banking sector moves from a transaction centric to a relationship centric business approach by focusing through "build good relationship" and the profitable transaction will follow automatically.

Review of Literature

During the course of the study the following research literature related to Customer relationship management were studied:

A Study on Customer Relationship Management Practices in Selected Private Sector Banks with Reference to Coimbatore District

Dr. H. Balakrishnan & R. Krishnaveni (2014)

In this study they have studied about the socio-economic characteristics of bank customers and its influence on CRM practices in selected private banks in Coimbatore district and also the relationship between the CRM practices and the attitude of the customers towards factors contributing to services quality and the customers perception towards CRM techniques in selected private sector banks and to offer suitable measures for improving the CRM practices in selected private banks. the purpose of study, a sampling survey was conducted among 150 customers of selected private sector banks namely Karur Vysya Bank, Lakshmi Vilas Bank, ICICI Bank with the help of a structured questionnaire. The tools used for this study are Percentage analysis, Likert's point scale analysis, Mean, Ranking method, Correlation and Chi – Square test.

Customer relationship management (CRM) success factors: an exploratory study

Mohammed Alamgir & Mohammad Shamsuddoha (2015)

In this study they have studied about Customer relationship management can enhance performance of the organization through effective application of customer knowledge and maintenance of relationships with valued customers and in this study they have find some factors like customer knowledge and social rapport. A Qualitative research approach has been taken in this study where ten customer-service managers of different telecom operators of Bangladesh have been interviewed. To determine the factors along with related variables and also to develop a research model, a content analysis technique has been utilized. The results of the interviews identified three factors affecting CRM success. This study also discusses about the implications of the model.

A Comparative Study of Customer Perception toward E-banking Services Provided By Selected Private & Public Sector Bank in India

Ms. Fozia (2013)

In this study the purpose was to determine the customer's perception toward the e-banking services. The study aims at identifying the overall customer perception towards the e-banking services. The study also aims at knowing whether demographic variables of the customer have influence on customer satisfaction on e- Banking and they also suggests that an understanding about the customer's perception regarding the e-banking services of public and private banks it will help to the banker to understand the customers need in better way.

A study on customer perception towards customer relationship management (CRM) practices in nationalised banks

Mr. T.Partha Saradhy, Dr. S.E.V.Subrahmanyam & Dr. T.Narayana Reddy (2014)

In this study they have studied about the customer relationship management practices are adopted to generate better understanding of the customers for product development, segmentation, appropriate targeting, campaign management and maintenance of long term profitable and mutually beneficial relationships with customers and analyze the perceived service quality of the customers towards their bankers and the CRM practices adopted by the banks to improve banking performance.

Customer Relationship Management in Banking Sector

Dr. V. Renuga & D. Durga (2016)

In this study they have studied about highly competitive business environment companies are not capable to longer survive with a transactional attitude towards customers and in this study they have studied to understand the concept of CRM and the CRM practices in Banking Sector and the benefits of CRM context in banking sector. The aim of this research is to develop a reliable and valid customer relationship management scale specifically catering to Indian banking sector. In the centre of marketing activities today is the customer satisfaction. For the banks to be successful in the intensively competitive environment, they are bound to attach importance to customer satisfaction.

Research Methodology

Title of the Study

“Study on The Perception Of Bank Executives on Customer relationship Management Practices in selected banks in Bengaluru.”

Statement of the problem

The success of modern banking and financial services depends on the customer relationship management practices adopted by them in acquiring new customers and retaining the existing customers with the prime focus on keeping them satisfied with value added services offered to them at their convenience.

However, the bank executives who are in direct contact with customers are expected to have a first hand knowledge of their expectations.

Therefore, this study is undertaken to understand the perceptions of bank executives on CRM practices in selected banks in one of the biggest commercial hubs in the country i.e., Bangalore, Karnataka.

Objectives

- To understand customer relationship management practices in selected banks in Bengaluru city
- To study the significant factors influencing CRM practices and customer satisfaction

Data collection

Primary Data – Primary data for the study purpose was collected through structured Questionnaire. Hundred Managers working in different bank branches were selected randomly for the study purpose. Secondary Data was collected from Books, Journals, Newspapers, RBI reports and annual reports of selected banks in Bangalore.

Sampling

The focus of this study was to establish the extent to which customer relationship management practices were being utilized within the Banking sector in Bengaluru. In Bengaluru, Banking sector is one of the booming sectors and having large number of branches, which involved in various products and services offered for customer satisfaction. As the focus of customer relationship management is on customer, it was decided to choose the component with the highest people concentration for the study, namely the banking sector. During the research period, the exact number of Banking sector in Bengaluru could not be established. In view of these restrictions, the researcher decided to compile a list of all the major Banks in Bengaluru, which are available in the Banking directories. From this directory the researcher has chosen 20 Banks, which have shown high profit margin continuously for three years as criteria.

Simple Random sampling method was employed to select the sample respondents from the selected 20 Banks 100 bank executives are selected on the basis of five executives from each bank.

Plan of Analysis

Factor Analysis is a method used to transform a set of variables into a small number of linear composites, which have a maximum correlation with original variables. Factor analysis is used to study a complex product (or) services, in order to identify the major characteristics or factors considered important by the respondents. The purpose of factor analysis is to determine whether the responses of several statements favoured by the respondents are significantly correlated. If the responses to the several statements are significantly correlated, it is considered that the statement measures some factors common to all of them.

Only to continuous variables or interval scales variables, the factor analysis can be applied. Factor analysis is a kind of regression analysis. The factor analysis attempts to get the 'best fit' factor from the scattered data in such an approach that factors describe the variance related to responses to each statement. The factor analysis was conducted in the following stages in the present research.

1. Secondary Research
2. Questionnaire formulation
3. Data collection
4. Input feeding and processing
5. Output analysis
6. Identifying the factors
7. Conclusions

FACTORS CHOSEN FOR THE ANALYSIS:

STATISTICS ASSOCIATED WITH FACTOR ANALYSIS:

Bartlett's test of sphericity- To test the null hypothesis that the variables chosen are not correlated with the sample universe Bartlett's test of sphericity can be used. The basis of this test is chi-square. During the process of calculations transformations of determination of correlation matrix is considered. The null hypothesis is rejected by a large value of test statistics.

Kaiser-Mayer-Olkin measure of sampling – The magnitude of partial correlation co-efficient is compared by this index, with the magnitude of the observed correlation co-efficient. Instant small values which specify the correlation between pairs of variables cannot be explained by other variables. With this indication, the factor analysis for evaluating a particular aspect will not be more appropriate.

Eigen Values and communalities – The sum of squared of its factor loading is indicated a factors Eigen value or latent route. How well a given factor fix the data gather from the sample respondents is given by Eigen value. The sum of squares of a statement's factor loading describes the communalities of each factor contributions for the selected variables.

A questionnaire was prepared covering the identified factors of the perception of bank officials on various aspects of CRM in their respective branches. All the selected 14 factors in the questionnaire of the present study were subjected for factor analysis by using Principle Component Analysis (PCA) with orthogonal rotation. There is no constraint on the number of factors. A factor loading cut off point of 0.50 was used for the sake of convergent validity.

The factor matrix is constructed with the help of matrix loading and correlations between the variables and factors. A loading of greater than 0.5 will be for pure variables. A higher loading is considered for complex variables which makes interpretation of the output difficult. To attain the significant variable the researcher rotated the components seven times under three factors.

Scope of the study

The study is confined to Bengaluru city in Karnataka. It was carried out for a period of three months between March to May 2017.

Results and Discussion

TABLE NO.1.0 shows the reliability statistics and proves the data could support 95.1 percentage reliable to do this analysis. TABLE NO.1.1 indicates that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measures of sampling adequacy in the study are 0.893. This is good result, as it exceeds 0.5. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity which is 0.000, meaning that factors that form the variables are adequate.

TABLE NO.1.0

RELIABILITY STATISTICS

The developed questionnaire has undergone Cronbach Alpha testing for testing its reliability and the value is given below:

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
0.951	34

TABLE NO.1.1

KMO AND BARTLETT'S TEST

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.893
Bartlett's Test of Approx. Chi-Square	2771.008
Sphericity	
Df	91
Sig.	.000

The following table shows the variables with the corresponding extraction communality factor value

TABLE NO.1.2

VARIABLE WITH EXTRACTED COMMUNALITY

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
ATM Spread and Network	1.000	.452
Service Options in ATM.	1.000	.570
Adequate Cheques-drop boxes.	1.000	.626
Issue /Renewal of credit/ATM cards.	1.000	.603
Issue of Monthly Statements.	1.000	.502
Responsiveness in counter service.	1.000	.556
Proper Safety on Internet banking.	1.000	.589
Face-to-Face interaction on demand.	1.000	.550
Safety and Security in ATM	1.000	.531
Transparency in Service charges	1.000	.497
Accuracy in account maintenance.	1.000	.705
Wide Acceptabilty of cards.	1.000	.423
Privacy in Account transactions.	1.000	.597
Timely Service on customer request.	1.000	.587
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

FACTOR VALUE – SIGNIFICANCE OF IMPACT OF CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

Factor 1	ATM Spread and Network
Factor 2	Service Options in ATM.
Factor 3	Adequate Cheque drop boxes.
Factor 4	Issue /Renewal of credit/ATM cards.
Factor 5	Issue of Monthly Statements.
Factor 6	Responsiveness in counter service.
Factor 7	Proper Safety on Internet banking.
Factor 8	Face-to-Face interaction on demand.
Factor 9	Safety and Security in ATM
Factor 10	Transparency in Service charges
Factor 11	Accuracy in account maintenance.
Factor 12	Wide Acceptabilty of cards.
Factor 13	Privacy in Account transactions.
Factor 14	Timely Service on customer request.

TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED

The following table No.1.3 reveals that the extraction has been undertaken by using principal-component method and the initial Eigen values are formulated from the communalities table and the same has been developed as extraction sums of squared loadings with percentage of variance and the relative cumulative percentage. From the initial Eigen values and the extraction sums of squared loadings values, the rotation sums of squared loadings has been formulated and shown in the following table.

Table No: 1.3 Total Variance – Perception of Bank Officials

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.587	47.053	47.053	6.587	47.053	47.053	4.732	33.801	33.801
2	1.201	8.579	55.632	1.201	8.579	55.632	3.056	21.832	55.632
3	.906	6.469	62.101						
4	.870	6.217	68.318						
5	.720	5.142	73.460						
6	.632	4.513	77.973						
7	.609	4.347	82.320						
8	.545	3.895	86.214						
9	.424	3.029	89.244						
10	.403	2.882	92.125						
11	.339	2.424	94.550						
12	.297	2.122	96.671						
13	.254	1.813	98.484						
14	.212	1.516	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

The extraction process has been carried out by using principal-component method, and it is found from the rotation sums of squared loadings and the total sum of 14 variables has been extracted and the same has been grouped into 2 components which have Eigen value of more than one. It ranges from component No. 1 to component No. 2 with the cumulative percentage from 33.801 percent to 55.632 percent. The percentage of variance ranges from 47.053% to 8.579%. For the second component of initial Eigen values, the total, percentage of variance and the cumulative percentage values are 1.078, 8.982% and 58.874 respectively. The extracted sum of squared loadings for the same is 1.201, 8.579% and 55.632 respectively. The rotation sum of squared loadings for the above is 3.056, 21.832 and 55.632 respectively.

From the analysis, it is inferred that the factor analysis has been supported up to 55.632% in this study. This is a good result and made the study reliable to the analysis.

The following Table No.1.4 has been formulated by using ‘principal-component method’ for extraction of variables into components and Varimax with Kaiser Normalization has been undergone by using ‘rotation method’. All the 14 variables have been grouped into two components and each component consists of sets of factors and the analysis has been made to identify the influence of one variable over another. The rotated component matrix is given in the following table. All the variables have significant factor loadings. The variables which have the maximum score of loadings are considered to be more important also has the greater influence on the factors selected.

TABLE NO: 1.4

ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX^a

	Component	
	1	2
ATM spread and Network	0.654	
Service Options in ATM.	0.647	
Adequate Cheque drop boxes.	0.790	
Issue /Renewal of credit/ATM cards.	0.603	
Issue of Monthly Statements.	0.530	
Responsiveness in counter service.	0.641	
Proper Safety on Internet banking.	0.589	
Face-to-Face interaction on demand.	0.550	
Wide Acceptability of cards.	0.627	
Transparency in Service charges.	0.663	
Accuracy in account maintenance.	0.765	
Safety and Security in ATM		0.711
Privacy in Account transactions		0.754
Timely Service on customer request.		0.697

Extraction method: Principal component Analysis.

Rotation method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

The factor analysis computer programme does not decide about the names or labels, rather the label is spontaneously developed by the factor analyst. All four factors have given appropriate names on the basis of the variable represented in each case.

The above table shows the rotated component matrix, in which the extracted factors are assigning a new naming related together. From the above table it is noted that all the loading factors which are having the loading value less than 0.5 are rejected from the analysis.

a) Factor 1 is the most important factor which explained 33.801% of the variation. The factors as ATM Spread and network (0.654), Service options in ATM (0.647), Adequate Cheque drop boxes (0.790), Issue /Renewal of credit/ATM cards (0.603), Issue of monthly statements (0.530), Responsiveness in counter service (0.641), Proper Safety on internet banking (0.589), Face-to-Face interaction on demand (0.511) Wide Acceptability of cards (0.627), Transparency in Service charges (0.663), and Accuracy in account maintenance (0.765) are highly correlated with each other. These

statements reflect the Bank Executives Effective Banking Services towards their work performance. Hence, the researcher names this segment respondents are **'Effective Banking Services factors'**.

b) The second kind of factors explained 21.832% of the variances. In this segment, the researchers took the three important variables such as Safety and Security in ATM (0.711), Privacy in Account transactions (0.754) and Timely Service on customer request (0.697). These statements are embossed the Security Services of the customer. Hence, the researcher coined the name as **'Security factors'**.

Conclusion

The present study has highlighted the significance of impact of customer relationship management practices has two categories like ATM Spread and network, Service Options in ATM, Adequate Cheque drop boxes, Issue/Renewal of credit/ATM cards, Issue of monthly statement, Responsiveness in counter service, Proper Safety on internet banking, Face-to-Face interaction on demand, Wide Acceptability of cards, Transparency Service and Accuracy in account have mostly influenced the characteristics of 'Effective Banking Services' factor. With the help of 'Effective Banking Services' factor the banking sector can increase their productivity and also the banks can attract their customer for longer period.

The factors like Safety Security, Privacy in account and Timely Service, plays an important role of Security services of the customer. Therefore these factors are grouped as 'Security factors'. With the help of 'Security factors' the customers are highly satisfied with safety and security services provided by the Banking sector which is more efficient. Therefore it has been concluded that 'Effective Banking Services factor' and 'Security factor' has become a coherent framework for a banking sector to increase their productivity and improve the various practices of CRM which can attract and retain the loyal customers.

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